

Deliverable D8.1

Federated access and federated learning technologies for advanced data analytics scenarios

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable, "*D8.1 Federated access and federated learning technologies for advanced data analytics scenarios*", presents the progress achieved within the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project towards enabling privacy-preserving, distributed data analysis across national genomic data nodes. It builds upon the architectural work of Pillar II and the use-case-driven activities of Pillar III to demonstrate, in practice, how federated processing can be achieved across the GDI ecosystem.

The document is structured around three complementary pillars of progress:

- Consolidation of the GDI Starter Kit architecture, which defines the baseline components required to enable federated data discovery, access, and computation.
- Implementation of a federated processing demonstrator, showcasing the feasibility of running distributed genome-wide association studies (GWAS) across multiple national nodes using GA4GH standards.
- Preparation for federated learning, establishing the conceptual and technical foundation for distributed model training as the next step in GDI's evolution.

The GDI Starter Kit provides a reference implementation of the core services required to operate a GDI node and to ensure interoperability across the infrastructure. While its scope extends beyond federated analysis alone, it also defines the baseline technical layout that enables compute-to-data execution in a distributed setting. The Starter Kit forms a reusable framework that partners can deploy locally to establish interoperable nodes aligned with GDI principles. Although the Starter Kit does not itself constitute a Secure Processing Environment (SPE), it provides the essential building blocks upon which national SPE implementations can be developed.

To translate this architecture into user-facing functionality, a set of user journeys was developed to describe interactions between end users and the infrastructure across different research scenarios. These journeys supported a transition from a component-centric to a feature-centric perspective, ensuring that infrastructure design remains aligned with real analytical workflows and researcher needs.

Building on this foundation, a Federated Processing Demonstrator was deployed in collaboration with the GDI Computational Task Force. Using synthetic data and a Snakemake-based GWAS workflow, the demonstrator executed distributed analyses across several national nodes. Workflow execution was coordinated via Funnel, an implementation of the GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES), which enabled compute-to-data execution at each node. An external Meta-GWAS aggregation step was subsequently performed. This exercise validated the interoperability of GDI components and highlighted practical gaps that must be addressed in future iterations.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers</p>	No

(e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.	
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	No

3. Background and Rational

The “D8.4 Report on federated data access scenarios”¹ defined the landscape of federated data access by identifying the technical and legal requirements to query, visualise, and process sensitive genomic data within a federation of trusted repositories. Key insights included the distinction between access modes, the relevance of permission granularity, and the use of containerised workflows to bring computation close to the data.

The “D8.5 Report on federated learning technologies”² expanded this perspective by reviewing federated learning technologies applicable to genomics and clinical data. It compared workflow and learning frameworks such as Galaxy³, DataSHIELD⁴, and Flower⁵, and gathered partner feedback on workflow managers (Nextflow⁶, Snakemake⁷, Galaxy). The study concluded that federated learning can achieve model performance comparable to centralised training while ensuring data sovereignty, aligning with the privacy principles of the 1+MG and GDI initiatives.

The “MS41 Initial Definition of the process to validate distributed and federated learning infrastructure on GDI”⁸ complemented these deliverables by describing the process for validation and delegation control of federated learning models, clarifying terminology (distributed vs federated; analysis vs learning) and identifying evaluation strategies using synthetic data.

Finally “D8.9 - Distributed analysis and federated learning PoC”, culminated in a demonstration of the current capabilities of the project towards federated analysis and learning. This effort was successful because of previous huge efforts on the project, where a collection of user journeys and user stories were built in collaboration between Pillar II and Pillar III members: the result in this deliverable.

4. Architecture for European Genomic Data Infrastructure

GDI provides the technical backbone for secure, federated access to genomic and phenotypic data across national nodes. Its implementation is grounded in the GDI Starter Kit, a modular, open-source package that enables each participating country to deploy a minimal but fully interoperable node of the federation.

The Starter Kit defines the reference architecture on which all subsequent GDI developments are built. It integrates the key GA4GH interoperability standards—the Data Repository Service (DRS) for dataset registration and access, the Workflow Execution Service (WES) and Task Execution Service (TES) for distributed computation, and a common Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/8208439>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/11550561>

³ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

⁴ <https://www.datashield.org/>

⁵ <https://flower.ai/>

⁶ <https://www.nextflow.io/>

⁷ <https://snakemake.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/11654040>

(AAI) based on LifeScience AAI (based on OpenID Connect (OIDC)). Through these components, nodes can expose discovery, access, and processing interfaces that are semantically and technically aligned across Europe.

The conceptual design and the first implementation guidelines were consolidated in the cross-pillar deliverables “D7.1 Use Case Demonstrator Package”⁹ and “D7.5 Recommendations for Addressing Use Cases”¹⁰, which describe how the Starter Kit components support real research scenarios and define the user-journey framework adopted in this deliverable.

4.1 Conceptual Model of Starter Kit

At the present stage, the GDI Starter Kit provides a reference implementation of the main components that enable each national node to interoperate within the European Genomic Data Infrastructure.

It is designed as a lightweight, modular deployment that allows partners to test the complete data lifecycle—from dataset registration to access and processing—using synthetic data and open-source components aligned with GA4GH standards.

The following table lists the main components currently included in the Starter Kit, mapped to the functional layers they support within the GDI architecture:

Component	Functional Layer	Purpose / Description
S3-compatible storage and metadata registry	Data Ingestion and Storage	Enable controlled deposition, organisation, and local hosting of genomic and phenotypic datasets within each node.
Beacon v2 services	Data Discovery and Access	Provide standardised, federated discovery interfaces that allow users to query datasets without exposing personal data.
User Portal	User Interface / Orchestration	Integrates data discovery, data availability, access management, and workflow initiation into a single entry point for users.
LifeScience AAI (OIDC)	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure	Manages federated identity and authentication across infrastructures, ensuring compliance with national and EU-level access policies.
REMS / Policy modules	Authorisation	Enable fine-grained access control and decision-making by Data Access Committees.

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/11635576>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/14537083>

Funnel	Processing Interfaces	Support the submission and orchestration of containerised workflows close to the data, implementing the "compute-to-data" paradigm (GA4GH TES API).
Container runtime (Docker / Singularity)	Processing Interfaces	Ensure reproducibility and portability of analyses across heterogeneous environments.
API gateway and orchestration services	User Interface / Integration	Provide standard entry points for automated access and inter-service communication between components.

As the Starter Kit evolved and matured during the project, it became apparent that while the selected components effectively delivered the necessary generic functionalities, the specific interactions and needs of real users had not been fully captured.

To address this, a set of user journeys was created to describe how different user profiles engage with the infrastructure and how the Starter Kit's components must interoperate to support their workflows. These user journeys complement the technical architecture by grounding it in concrete research processes, ensuring that GDI evolves according to the needs and expectations of its intended users.

The outcomes of this activity are presented in **Results** of this deliverable.

4.2 Starter kit towards the Federated Infrastructure

Building on the architecture provided by the GDI Starter Kit, the Computational Task Force, in close collaboration with WP8, designed and implemented a federated processing demonstrator to evaluate how the existing infrastructure could support distributed computation across national nodes.

This activity had a dual purpose:

- To showcase what is already technically achievable with the components provided by the Starter Kit and the wider GDI ecosystem.
- To identify the missing architectural, operational, and procedural elements required to evolve towards a fully functional, production-grade federated data analytics infrastructure.

This work followed a "*build-to-learn*" philosophy. By deploying and testing a real workflow across multiple nodes, the demonstrator was able to validate interoperability in practice, assess the behaviour of GA4GH APIs under real workloads, and identify integration challenges between Pillar II (infrastructure and services) and Pillar III (data use cases).

5. Results

This section summarises the practical outcomes of the activities conducted to test, validate, and extend the capabilities of the GDI Starter Kit, especially with an eye on distributed and federated analysis.

Two main results emerged:

1. The definition of User Journeys describing how future users will interact with the infrastructure
2. The successful implementation of a Federated Processing Demonstrator that tested the operational maturity of the current GDI architecture.

5.1 GDI User Journey description document

While the GDI project progressively refined the design of the Starter Kit, it became evident that a clear understanding of how its components interact at the operational level was still missing.

To address this gap, Pillar II and Pillar III collaborated on the creation of a compendium of User Journeys: a series of narrative descriptions of how different categories of users (researchers, clinicians, data stewards, and infrastructure operators) interact with the system to achieve their respective goals.

Each user journey describes a specific set of actions and services involved in a particular phase of interaction with the system. Some journeys represent partial or prerequisite steps that can be reused as building blocks within broader user journeys.

The journeys document, therefore, translates the abstract design of the Starter Kit into realistic end-to-end operational pathways, ensuring that the infrastructure evolves to meet concrete user expectations and legal constraints.

The resulting "*GDI User Journey Description Document*" (Annex I) captures these workflows across major use-case categories such as rare diseases, infectious diseases, cancer, and population genomics.

It provides both a validation framework for current developments and a blueprint for future service extensions, helping align technical evolution with user-driven priorities across the federation.

5.2 Demonstrator: Distributed GWAS + Meta-GWAS

5.2.1 Implementation Approach

The demonstrator reused and extended the Starter Kit components, integrating them into a multi-node execution pipeline capable of performing a distributed Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS) followed by a meta-GWAS aggregation step.

Each participating node analysed local synthetic datasets, producing summary statistics that were later aggregated into a combined result without sharing personal data at any point.

The reference stack consisted of the following layers and technologies:

Layer	Technology	Function
Workflow Manager	<i>Snakemake</i>	Defines reproducible GWAS workflow and manages execution logic.
Task API	<i>GA4GH TES via Funnel</i>	Executes containerised jobs on each node through a standard task interface.
Container Runtime	<i>Docker</i>	Encapsulates execution environments to ensure portability and reproducibility.
Storage	<i>S3-compatible buckets</i>	Provides per-node input/output storage; supports connections to multiple endpoints.
Identity & Access	<i>LifeScience AAI (OIDC)</i>	Provides federated authentication and authorisation; static credentials used for the PoC.
Aggregation Layer	<i>Meta-GWAS module</i>	Combines local GWAS summary statistics without sharing raw data.

This workflow was tested across several partner nodes (e.g., Czech Republic, Spain, Portugal, Germany, Norway, Sweden, Finland) using synthetic data.

The Czech node performed the full web-to-TES execution loop, while others validated local execution through their Funnel-based endpoints.

5.2.2 Key Achievements

The demonstrator achieved the following milestones:

- Operational validation of the GA4GH TES standard in a multi-node configuration, confirming interoperability with the Starter Kit's AAI and storage layers.

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- Demonstration of privacy-preserving¹¹ analytics, with all computation confined within national SPEs and only aggregated, non-identifiable outputs shared.
- Proven portability of containerised workflows (Snakemake + Docker), enabling reproducible execution across heterogeneous environments.
- Strengthened cross-pillar collaboration, providing a tangible link between Pillar II technical services and Pillar III scientific use cases.

5.2.3 Insights and Identified Gaps

Beyond demonstrating feasibility, the exercise highlighted several areas requiring further development to reach full production maturity:

- Need for automated token exchange between orchestrators and TES endpoints to replace static credentials.
- Implementation of standardised egress mechanisms for secure publication of uniform aggregated results.
- Enhanced metadata propagation to track provenance and facilitate discovery of executed workflows.
- Uniform monitoring and logging strategies to ensure auditability and reproducibility across the federation.
- Development of templated workflow packages to simplify deployment of new federated analyses beyond GWAS.

6. Discussion

- End-to-end federated execution was not fully automated: authentication propagation and result aggregation required manual intervention.
- Workflow orchestration was not natively integrated into the Starter Kit, relying instead on external components for execution and coordination.
- Dynamic workflow discovery and execution were not realised, as workflows were preconfigured rather than retrieved from a federated workflow repository.
- The demonstrated architecture remains partially generic, applicable to both centralised and distributed setups, with explicit federated behaviour emerging mainly at the aggregation stage.
- The demonstrator focused on proof of feasibility rather than production readiness, leaving scalability, robustness, and operational hardening for future work.

¹¹Funnel and OAuth2: <https://ohsu-comp-bio.github.io/funnel/docs/security/oauth2/#oauth2>

6.1. From architecture to features through user journeys

The development of the Starter Kit provided a generic foundational architecture for data access and processing that can, in principle, support both centralised and distributed/federated deployments. However, it was through the definition and analysis of user journeys that this architecture began to be shaped explicitly towards federated usage scenarios, evolving from a purely technical stack into a feature-oriented, user-centred ecosystem.

These user journeys captured the concrete interactions and requirements of researchers engaging with a distributed infrastructure, spanning dataset discovery, access request, local workflow execution at national nodes, and downstream result aggregation. In doing so, they complemented the architectural work of Pillar II by expressing, in operational terms, how individual components must cooperate when computation is deliberately brought to the data rather than centralised.

The process also enabled systematic mapping of Pillar III use cases to functional capabilities, identifying which Starter Kit components already supported distributed execution and which required further development to operate in a federated context. Among the evaluated scenarios, the GWAS use case was selected as the most suitable candidate for an initial federated demonstrator. This choice was driven by its reliance on clearly separable local computations and a final aggregation step, making it a natural fit for a privacy-preserving, compute-to-data paradigm.

6.2. Demonstrating federated analysis and aggregation

The federated processing demonstrator validated the feasibility of distributed analysis across multiple national nodes, explicitly exercising a federated execution model rather than a centralised one. Using synthetic data, each node performed local GWAS computations, after which a Meta-GWAS step aggregated results externally. This separation between local execution and global aggregation constituted the clearest manifestation of federated behaviour within the demonstrator.

While this approach successfully demonstrated that federated computation and aggregation can be achieved using current GA4GH-aligned infrastructure, it also revealed several important operational limitations of the current Starter Kit implementation:

- **Authentication propagation.** Tokens could not be automatically exchanged between components (AAI ↔ TES), requiring manual credential setup.
- **Result retrieval and aggregation.** Output aggregation was executed outside the workflow orchestration, requiring manual collection of node outputs.
- **Orchestration and workflow.** The automatic orchestration of the analytical workflow relied on components external to the Starter Kit: the SeqUla orchestrator and the Snakemake workflow manager. The workflow was preconfigured within the orchestrator rather than being dynamically obtained from a workflow repository or hub.

These gaps highlight that, while the architectural building blocks for federated analysis are in place, key integration points remain unresolved. Addressing these limitations is essential to move from a demonstrator that proves feasibility to a production-grade, fully automated federated infrastructure aligned with Pillar III requirements.

7. Conclusions

- Validated a functional federated processing model for genomic data across European national nodes, demonstrating the feasibility of compute-to-data execution.
- Confirmed interoperability across heterogeneous infrastructures through the combined use of GA4GH standards, container-based workflows, and a harmonised authentication framework.
- Identified technical and procedural gaps that must be addressed to transition from prototype demonstrators to production-ready services.
- Strengthened alignment between infrastructure and user needs through coordinated work between Pillars II and III.
- Established a foundation for scalable, privacy-preserving federated learning within the European Genomic Data Infrastructure.

The work presented in this deliverable demonstrates that the European Genomic Data Infrastructure has reached a significant level of maturity in enabling federated data access and federated processing. By combining GA4GH standards, container-based workflows, and a harmonised authentication framework, the project has validated a realistic and reproducible pathway towards compute-to-data execution within national nodes.

The federated demonstrator functioned both as a proof of concept and as a diagnostic instrument. It confirmed interoperability across heterogeneous technical environments while simultaneously exposing the specific technical, organisational, and procedural elements that require further refinement in order to move from research-grade prototypes to sustainable operational services.

Crucially, the collaboration between Pillars II and III ensured close alignment between infrastructure design and user-facing requirements. This integration strengthens the likelihood that future GDI services will be not only technically robust, but also usable and responsive to real research needs.

Overall, this deliverable represents a transition point for GDI: moving beyond the establishment of a baseline federated processing environment and towards the preparation of scalable, secure, and privacy-preserving federated learning capabilities across Europe's distributed genomic data landscape.

8. Next steps

Building on the lessons learned from the federated processing demonstrator, the next phase focuses on Federated Learning, extending the compute-to-data paradigm to collaborative machine learning

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models. The vision is to allow model training across distributed datasets, where only *model parameters* or *gradients* are exchanged, never personal data.

This next phase is designed to directly address the operational gaps identified in the **Discussion**, in particular those related to authentication propagation, workflow orchestration, result handling, and data interoperability.

Planned evolution towards a Federated Learning demonstrator

The upcoming Federated Learning Demonstrator (outlined in Annex 2: *GDI – Federated Learning*) will implement the following steps:

1. **Unified Entry Point:** Users access the Federated Analytics Dashboard via the main GDI user portal, integrated with LS AAI for secure authentication.
2. **Data Discovery and Access:** Users identify and request access to uniform datasets ("*D2.8 Evaluation of the potential legal frameworks for the infrastructure*"¹²) distributed across nodes using the central Data Catalogue and access management tools (REMS).
3. **Framework and Workflow Selection:** From the Federated Analytics Dashboard, users select among available federated learning frameworks and workflows.
4. **Experiment Configuration:** Users package their model and configure the experiment parameters, selecting participating nodes and datasets.
5. **Federated Execution:** The orchestrator distributes training jobs to the nodes, which perform local model updates on their own data. An aggregator node collects and combines model weights or gradients according to the selected framework.
6. **Result Collection and Cleaning:** The final model is stored in the user space and made available for download; intermediate data and temporary model updates are securely deleted according to defined policies.

Expected impact

This workflow operationalises the federated learning principles defined by the project: secure, distributed model training with controlled orchestration, strong data locality, semantic interoperability, and reproducibility. It also directly addresses the shortcomings observed in the federated processing demonstrator by embedding token-based authentication, automated orchestration, and integrated result handling.

The development and deployment of this Federated Learning Demonstrator will thus represent the next major step in consolidating GDI's federated architecture and validating its readiness for production-scale, privacy-preserving analytics.

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/8208479>

Annex I. GDI User Journey Description Document

A1.1. Glossary

- **(Data) User.** An identified, authenticated real person belonging to a research or health organisation that uses GDI infrastructure. A user has a series of connotations according to their background according to the HealthyCloud user profiles and sub-profiles¹³, the 1+MG Governance and ELSI¹⁴, and the 1+MG Glossary¹⁵:
 - **Researchers.** Researchers are those individuals that will interact with GDI's infrastructure with the goal to obtain, process, and/or analyse research data and its potentially associated outcomes.
 - **Healthcare professional.** A healthcare professional is a person that has an active role in processing, analysing and/or understanding health-related data. Their main goal while using GDI's infrastructure is to obtain knowledge that could be transferred to clinical practice.
 - **Policy maker.** It is a person, or group of people, responsible for or involved in formulating policies¹⁶, especially in politics and related to healthcare. In order to fulfil their duties, they might need to access high level statistics of GDI, usage of GDI's data, or GDI's data in its fraction or completeness. A user also includes consultancies who develop policies for a policy maker.
- **Data provider.** According to the definition in HealthyCloud¹, a data provider is a person or entity that generates and/or makes available health-related data into the 1+MG, either as a product of their activity or as mandated by another individual or organisation. The data provider may not be the one who has collected the data. The data provider does not act vis-a-vis the user but transfers the (legal) responsibility for the disclosure to the user to the Genome EDIC. Then, the 1+MG Governance and ELSI², and the 1+MG Glossary³ requires for extra detail:
 - **Data controller (can be a joint controller).** Data controllers are those that, as a natural or legal person, as well as a public authority, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of processing GDI's data or a subset of it (for instance the data in a national node). A data controller does not require to have access to the data nor to host it

¹³ FAIR Health Data Portal expected users' interactions: <https://zenodo.org/records/10225882>

¹⁴ 1+MG Governance and ELSI: <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/governance-elsi>

¹⁵ 1+MG Glossary - version for 1+MG Framework: <https://zenodo.org/records/8279620>

¹⁶ Health Researchers and Policy Makers: A Need to Strengthen Relationship: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3191660/>

to exercise the role. In addition, a data controller is a qualification under the GDPR and changes along the data life cycle.

- Data provider are controllers for bringing data into the Genome EDIC
- The Genome EDIC is controller for the disclosure to the user
- The user is controller for the data use such as a research project
- When we have subject-level data discovery in advance for an access request, the user and EDIC are joint controllers for those operations.
- **Data host.** A natural or legal person, a public authority, or a third party entity (such as Amazon, Microsoft or Google) that stores any subset of GDI's data, usually on behalf of another entity (usually a data controller).
- **IT infrastructure provider.** It is a legal person, as well as public authority, that contributes to GDI by providing physical and/or computational infrastructure to achieve the project's goals in terms of data storage capabilities, data processing capabilities, and/or logistic operative support capabilities to enable meeting the project's long-term needs.
 - **Data processor.** According to the 1+MG Glossary³, a Data processor is a natural or legal person, as well as public authority, which processes personal and/or health data on behalf of the Data controller.
- **(Data) Processing.** Data processing covers any sort of process (including holding data) covering the non exhausting aspects of training AI models, analysis of clinical and/or genetic data for research purposes, identification of shared pathologies across datasets (both using clinical and/or genetic data to do so) or high level or low level statistics on data collections, data sets or individual records.
- **Data.** Any digital information susceptible to being used in health research and regulated by previously mentioned laws and stored within GDI's premises.
 - **(Individual) Record.** Data related to individual data subjects.
 - **Data set.** Individual records that are grouped in a certain context (for example: project that generated the "data", clinical condition definition, etc.). they can be characterised using non-personal metadata.
 - **Data collection.** Data sets that are grouped together in a certain context, and coming from the same data controller(s). They can be characterised with non-personal metadata. A data collection, for instance, refers to data of a cohort or public registry.
 - **Clinical data.** Personal data related to the physical or mental health of an individual data subject independent of its origin (e.g. from healthcare, research, clinical trials contexts - among others). In 1+MG's Glossary this is referred to as "health data", with other granularity as "healthcare data" and "health research data"; in other projects "phenotypic

data” is also used to describe this information and in Beacon v2 it is called “phenoclinic data”.

- **Genetic data.** Personal data related to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of an individual which give unique information about their physiology or health, and which results from an analysis of a biological sample from the individual question.

A1.2. Workflow

A1.3. GDI researcher user journeys

A1.3.1 Authenticate into GDI Federation

#: ujGdi01	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ
<p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User belongs to a recognized research or health organisation - User's national node uses a compatible and configured IAM <p>Description:</p> <p>User aims to authenticate to any of GDI central services. The user goes to the selected central service and is able to, leveraging their national node's IAM solution, log in into central services properly authenticated with their national digital identity.</p>	

A1.3.2. Data Discovery using User Portal's Data Catalogue for Authenticated Users

#: ujGdi02	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: ND, LP, EGJ, GC, TP, LW
<p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data catalogue is defined and included in the GDI User Portal, displaying the metadata for each dataset discoverable. The Data Catalogue will provide basic and advanced querying and filtering options to the user. Currently the data catalogue is open access as it does not include any personal data and can be explored without logging in. - The metadata is granular enough to help the user identify the right datasets - The user understands what metadata from GDI's datasets is relevant for their purpose. <p>Description:</p> <p>A user aims to discover datasets of interest. The user explores the Data Catalogue and uses the search and filter functionalities to identify the datasets that align with their objectives and requirements.</p>	

This search is done based only on metadata associated with each dataset, that metadata can be downloaded if the user wishes to do so.

Postconditions:

- None

A1.3.3. Data Discovery using GDI's Beacon Network for Authenticated Users

#: ujGdi03	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: ND, LP, CHF, EGJ
<p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Following ujGdi01 <p>Description:</p> <p>A user aims to discover datasets of interest. They access the GDI's User Portal and authenticate following ujGdi01. Once logged in, the user decides to explore the data by performing a Beacon' clinical and/or genomic query through a search box.</p> <p>This query relies on the GDI capabilities of searching over dataset according to the actual phenoclinic and genomic data in the datasets. The response obtained from GDI's Infrastructure includes the number of individuals in each dataset that meet the properties defined at the query among other information.</p> <p>Postconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None 	

A1.3.4. Data Access Request

#: ujGdi04	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF, JMF, ND, LP, LW, TP, GC
<p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user has already identified the datasets of interest (usGdi02 or ujGdi03). - The user authenticates themselves in GDI following ujGdi01 - The user has read and understood the "GDI / 1+MG Data Access workflow": - The datasets can be discriminated to such a degree so the user can identify which part of them is useful to their research to ensure that "data minimization" (according to GDI internal suggestion) can be achieved. - The data request form in Data Catalogue will provide self explanatory information to be filled as well as functionality to "save drafts" of partially filled requests for further submission. - The user will provide enough information on their application to not be rejected based on technicalities. At the same time, the individual(s) reviewing the application will have enough detailed knowledge to properly evaluate a user petition. <p>Description:</p> <p>A user aims to request access to datasets of interest. The user selects the datasets of interest using the User Portal and requests access to them. The user fills out the relevant forms, where what is requested is reasonable and relevant guidance is readily available. The user expects that they will only be able to submit the form once they have supplied sufficient information.</p> <p>The user might leave the application for an extended period, and return to it once they have acquired the information that is sufficient to fill out the application. Using the User Portal, the user submits the application. The user will be notified once a decision on their application is made, reflecting the outcome.</p> <p>Postconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user has a preliminary decision on their access request. <p>Needs discussion and clarification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None 	

A1.3.5. Positive application response

#: ujGdi05	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF, LP
<p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user has completed data access request user journey (ujGdi04) <p>Description:</p> <p>The user is notified, within the accorded deliberation time, through one of the official channels regarding the updated status of his/her petition.</p> <p>This update communication may include access conditions to the requested data such as the date when access may be exercised or validity period during which the access is valid.</p> <p>Postconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user gets access to the requested datasets - The valid access permission is registered in the appropriate infrastructure. <p>Needs discussion and clarification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None 	

A1.3.6. Amend an application

#: ujGdi06	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF, LP
<p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user has completed data access request user story (ujGdi04) <p>Description:</p> <p>The user is notified, within the accorded deliberation time, through one of the official channels regarding the updated status of his/her petition.</p>	

With the petition rejection, the committee may ask for the user to amend the petition and include extra information required to come to a decision.

The user is then able to complete the petition and, once all the information asked for has been included, resubmit the application by following the user story ([ujGdi04](#))

Postconditions:

- The user gets access to the requested datasets
- The valid access permission is registered in the appropriate infrastructure.

Needs discussion and clarification:

- None

A1.3.7. Data Applications Overview (for granted access data)

<p>#: ujGdi07</p>	<p>Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional</p>
	<p>Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF</p>
<p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user has already identified the datasets of interest (ujGdi01). - The user has already requested access to one or more datasets of interest (ujGdi03) and data access has been granted. - A user may have different accounts when working in healthcare with a hospital affiliation and in research with an affiliation in a research organisation; the user may also access under the same affiliation for healthcare and for research purposes, leading to different rights in accessing the data, which always has to be separated. <p>Description:</p> <p>A user wishes to check which datasets they have access to at a given time point. To do so, the user accesses the GDI's User Portal and follows user journey usjGdi01.</p> <p>On the User Portal, a page displays the list of petitions they have requested, each detailing the set of data-sets they are requesting access to, the dates of creation and last modification and their approval status.</p> <p>Postconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user understands the definition of each status code. - User's profile gets filled in with the visas for the requested datasets. 	

A1.3.8. Federated Data Computation

#: ujGdi08	Story name: The user triggers an analysis in several Secure Processing Environment (SPE) to run the user's computation of interest
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, LC, CHF, LP, SCG, LW, TP, GC
<p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user already has been authenticated and requested access to several datasets across several nodes as per usGdi04, and has been approved as per ujGdi05. - The user has selected an approved workflow that will perform the computation of interest (ujGdi10). <p>Description:</p> <p>A user accesses the Federated Data Computation Dashboard and selects the workflow of interest, as well as the datasets of interest where the workflow will be run. Then, the user provides parameters requested by each task of the analytical workflow using the Federated Computation Dashboard.</p> <p>The user, from a known organisation gains, access to a national SPE, where data is made available to them (see preconditions). Depending on the project the user is involved in, the user is authorised to certain datasets.</p> <p>The user chooses among the analysis tools available for them at the SPE. It sets up the run parameters and input files.</p> <p>The archived datasets are made accessible at the SPE on behalf of the user. In case storage's credentials are not integrated in LS-AAI, the user will provide them to the SPE directly.</p> <p>The SPE makes the datasets available to the run computing environment, ready to be consumed by the analysis and visualisation tools.</p> <p>The user obtains the analysis output at its SPE private workspace. Depending on the data type associated with the output, they can (1) be visualised at the SPE using a visualisation tool, (2) further analysed using other analysis tools, (3) be downloaded (ujGdi09) from the SPE (with previous validation by the SPE data governance officer).</p>	

Postconditions:

- Any information private to the user's researcher will not be distributed with any other entity.

A1.3.9. Download analytical (and mostly aggregated) results

#: ujGdi09	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF

Preconditions:

- The user has executed an analysis following [ujGdi08](#).
- The user has been granted access to the results of the analysis executed (all nodes had vetoed the results).
- All nodes can connect the other nodes with the purpose of accessing the results of that user executions they have stored.

The analytical workflow the user selected is composed by two sections: 1) a series of tasks that must be run in multiple national nodes to extract key information from the datasets of interest by the researcher, to generate intermediate results ([ujGdi08](#)); 2) an extra step that will aggregate the results from the previous step in a single “final result” ([ujGdi08](#)).

There will be scenarios where the second step is not necessary and what is called “partial final results” are, in fact, the “final results” (one in each of the involved national nodes).

To the user, it is key to be able to download both the “partial final results” and the “final result” of the selected analytical workflow in order to pursue their research.

The national node the researcher belongs to will be the one in charge to collect the “partial final results”. If the second step (aggregation) is necessary, it will also be responsible to make the aggregation (for example, the meta analysis done from multiple GWAS analysis). Then, both the “partial final results” and the “final result” should be accessible from the user’s node.

Postconditions:

- Both “partial final results” and “final results” are accessible by the user at the end of [ujGdi08](#) + [ujGdi09](#) (this user journey).
- Other nodes involved in [ujGdi08](#) are allowed to delete temporary results after some time of [ujGdi08](#)

A1.3.10. Submission of an analytical workflow

#: ujGdi10	Triggered by User Role:
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF

Preconditions

- The user authenticates themselves in GDI following [ujGdi01](#)
- The user understands GDI's Federated Computation Dashboard features and how to define an analytical workflow.

Description

The user has an idea of an analytical workflow in order to answer their scientific questions, for which they want to use the GDI infrastructure and data resources.

In order to do so, the user inspects the Marketplace, where all the applications (software and models) reside. Picking from the list and concatenating the different applications, the user is able to create a new analytical workflow, either using a graphical user interface application such as the Federated Computation Dashboard or using a workflow description language.

Once the user has the analytical workflow defined, they can submit it to acceptance into GDI using the same Federated Computation Dashboard. GDI will answer the user in a reasonable amount of time. During this time GDI will: A) check that the analytical workflow does not leak any data nor performs any undesired operation, and B) inform the national nodes about the new workflow, which will have some time (within the original reasonable amount of time) to test the workflow and raise any technical issues in which case they can request changes be made to the workflow and the application to begin anew. If both A and B are successful, [ujGdi11](#). Otherwise [ujGdi12](#).

Postconditions

- The analytical workflow is submitted into GDI's system and accessible by GDI's staff and national nodes for its validation.

A1.3.11. Acceptance of an analytical workflow

#: ujGdi11	Triggered by User Role: Technical personal from national SPE
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF
Preconditions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user authenticates themselves in GDI following ujGdi01. - The user has submitted an analytical workflow for validation. 	

Description

The GDI validation committee receives a notification from GDI's Federation Commutation Dashboard indicating that an analytical workflow has been submitted for validations.

The committee inspects the multiple tasks of the workflow to ensure no data is leaked during its execution and that all the operations performed are permeated in the project.

Seeing that all the tasks are correct, the committee notifies the national nodes for local testing. The national nodes will be given a reasonable amount of time to locally test the workflow if desired. After that amount of time expires or if they submit a positive result, the analytical workflow will be flagged as acceptable.

The validation committee will collect all the feedback from the national nodes and, finding them all (actively or passively) positive, they flag the analytical workflow as accepted. Doing so, the GDI's Federated Computational Dashboard will now include the analytical workflow as usable by GDI's user and will notify the owner of the positive validation results.

Postconditions

- The analytical workflow is now listed as usable within GDI federated computation infrastructure.
- The user that submitted the workflow is notified of the positive results.

A1.3.12. Denial of an analytical workflow

#: ujGdi12	Triggered by User Role: Technical personal from national SPE
	Authors and Contributors: EGJ, CHF
Preconditions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user authenticates themselves in GDI following ujGdi01. - The user has submitted an analytical workflow for validation. 	
Description <p>The GDI validation committee receives a notification from GDI's Federation Commutation Dashboard indicating that an analytical workflow has been submitted for validations.</p>	

The committee inspects the multiple tasks of the workflow to ensure no data is leaked during its execution and that all the operations performed are permeated in the project.

If the committee identifies a possible data leak or that some of the operations performed by the analytical workflows are unacceptable within GDI's context, they flag the analytical workflow as rejected (indicating which operations are leaking data and/or which operations are not accepted).

If the committee sees that all the tasks are correct, the committee then notifies the national nodes for local testing. The national nodes will be given a reasonable amount of time to locally test the workflow if desired.

During that time the national nodes can test the analytical workflow. If they identify technical or legal issues that forbids them to run the workflow locally, they will document the issue and tag the workflow as unacceptable.

Either because the validation committee flagged the analytical workflow as unacceptable or because some national node reported issues, the workflow is reported not to be accepted in GDI's system. In doing so, the GDI's Federated Computational Dashboard will notify the owner of the negative validation, providing useful feedback that can be used to fix the reported issues. The workflow then could be submitted again to GDI's network.

Postconditions

- The analytical workflow was not included in GDI's system.
- The user that submitted the workflow is notified of the negative results and useful feedback is provided in order to create a new analytical workflow with the same functionality but that has higher possibilities to be accepted in GDI.

A1.4. GDI user stories born from user journeys

A1.4.1. Enabling contact with treating healthcare professional

<p>#: usGdi01</p>	<p>Soft description: The user wants to set up a communication channel with the relevant clinical contact related to patients with the same genetic and/or clinical condition as theirs to discuss possible outcomes</p> <p>Triggered by User Role: Health professional</p> <p>Authors and Contributors: MM, EB, GG, FC, LP, CHF, GC, TB</p>
<p>Precondition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user must be authenticated, authorised, and valid for GDI. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Doing a query constitutes a “data processing” activity; therefore the organisation where the user belongs needs to have a data-use agreement with Genome-EDIC. <p>Description:</p> <p>A user has an individual case with a particular genetic and/or clinical description. In order to proceed with caution, they want to contact other healthcare professionals that dealt with similar cases.</p> <p>The user will follow the process described in “Look up the frequency of variants in GDI” (usGdi02) to identify datasets containing similar individuals to the one of their interest.</p> <p>The user goes back to the relevant communication channel in the User Portal and describes their case-in-question (providing the ids of datasets of interest) and submits it, expecting a notification when the communication channel between them is available in a specified time frame.</p> <p>Postconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user ends up having the relevant contact of their specific case mediated through the Use Portal (aka, relevant communication channel). - Although included in the data-use agreement, the user will not, under any setting, contact any patient discovered using this user story. 	

A1.4.2. Patients diagnosed with metastatic melanoma

#: usGdi01.1	Soft description: Enabling contact with treating healthcare professional for a patient diagnosed with metastatic melanoma
	Triggered by User Role: Clinician/oncologist
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case
<p>User story description:</p> <p>The use case is a refinement of usGdi01 (Enabling contact with treating healthcare professionals to discuss possible outcomes related to patients with similar genetic or clinical conditions) to a real case scenario.</p> <p>A clinician needs to find a second therapeutic option for his/her patient diagnosed with metastatic melanoma, justified by the identification of possible targetable mutation(s). A secondary objective is to find the molecular alterations explaining the emergence of the resistance of the primary cancer treatment.</p> <p>The goal is to find a similar case in the GDI databases, by querying the network, i.e. find melanoma patients with a BRAF point mutation, treated with BRAF inhibitor Vemurafenib, who have a mutation in the PTEN gene (known variant responsible for therapy resistance). The goal is to search for existing information on the PTEN gene, the BRAF mutation and the impact of the mutation on the Kinase pathway that can explain drug resistance in melanoma cancer patients.</p> <p>Preconditions: The clinician must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The clinician logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01) and browses available datasets (ujGdi02 or ujGdi03). • The clinician inputs a Beacon query (ujGdi03) using genomic coordinates or gene fusion terms, to find patients with a PTEN deletion in the genomic data. Data are filtered to focus on the most relevant cases: patients with melanoma and with details concerning the characteristics of the patient, the responses to the treatment, and survival rates. 	

#: usGdi01.1	Soft description: Enabling contact with treating healthcare professional for a patient diagnosed with metastatic melanoma
	Triggered by User Role: Clinician/oncologist
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The GDI returns results, which may include a dataset relative to another patient with a similar disease and therapy history, found on one node of the network. The dataset is composed of genetic data (NGS sequencing of a melanoma treated with Vemurafenib, after developing resistance to the therapy) and the corresponding clinical data. Both raw genetic data (.Fastq file) and analysed data (.vcf file containing somatic mutations and BED file containing structural alterations) are present. Aggregated data could be visualised via a visualisation tool like in cBioportal. • If needed, a communication channel with the relevant clinical contact related to the identified patient(s) can be set up. • The clinician applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). • The clinician downloads the genetic sequence data with the corresponding clinical data of the identified patient(s) (ujGdi09). <p>Postconditions: -</p>	

A1.4.3. Look up variant summary data in and across GDI datasets

#: usGdi02	Soft description: Look up variant summary data in and across GDI datasets
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: LW, GC, TP, CHF
<p>User story description: “As a [clinician/researcher/policy maker], I would like to look up the frequency of a given allele in a given [disease, disease type, population, ancestry...] in order to [interrogate pathogenicity of the allele/infer the efficacy of a know drug using pharmacogenomics knowledge/...]”</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A database containing the following precomputed information on each allele present: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Beacon - Dataset - Population - Genetic Ancestry Group - Genome Build - Allele Count - Allele Number - Homozygous Count - Hemizygous Count - Female Count - Male Count - A user-friendly central web application to perform the query - Web application should state <i>“The information on this website is not intended for direct diagnostic use or medical decision-making without review by a genetics professional. Individuals should not change their health behaviour solely on the basis of information contained on this website. If you have questions about the information contained on this website, please see a healthcare professional.”</i> - from https://clinicalgenome.org/about/ or similar <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User visits a web application that looks something like the following: 	

#: usGdi02	Soft description: Look up variant summary data in and across GDI datasets
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: LW, GC, TP, CHF

User input

HOW

<https://afb.gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu>

The user can query this system from a centralised web application.

European Genomic Data Infrastructure

Allele Frequency Browser

Specify genome build

hg38

Specify cohort(s) (or all)

GoE

Input handling - only in format chr-pos-ref-alt

If not entered in this format, inform user to use this format

Search for a variant....

Example search: 13-32398489-A-T

Give an example query

- Demo exists here: <https://af-browser-demo.ega-archive.org/>
- The user performs a genomic query searching for a variant using the format chr-pos-ref-alt through GDI's federated querying system, with the ability to specify the genome build and cohort/dataset (or all cohorts/datasets)

#: usGdi02	Soft description: Look up variant summary data in and across GDI datasets
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: LW, GC, TP, CHF

Postconditions:

- The output should look something like:

<https://afb.gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/variant/13-32398489-A-T>

Variant: 13-32398489-A-T (hg38)

HOW

Link to same variant in other databases (particularly to underserved cohorts)

Pathogenicity predictors

External links

- link to ClinVar
- link to gnomAD
- link to ALLOFUS

In Silico Predictors

- REVEL
- SpliceAI
- etc

Ancestry	Allele Count	Allele Number	Homozygous/Hemizygous Count	Allele Frequency
Non-Finnish European	8532	917658	44	0.0093
African	24	18456	0	0.0013

[Feedback](#)

Some datasets will be aligned to different reference genomes

[Liftover to same variant on hg19](#)

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

- This type of data could be used for:
 - Clinical and research variant interpretation (overseen by a genetics professional)
 - Check if your patient's variant is present in similar patient cohorts (e.g. <https://epi25.broadinstitute.org/>)

Needs discussion and clarification:

- One possible function of GDI would be to create a gnomAD-like portal but for the European population and for disease cohorts. With GoE data, this could be achieved but it might not be the goal of the project. Moreover, the remaining datasets and data collections within GDI could

#: usGdi02	Soft description: Look up variant summary data in and across GDI datasets
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher and/or health professional
	Authors and Contributors: LW, GC, TP, CHF
be included into this “resource/service” but to do so, the data access policy and its granularity (beyond public/private) needs to be defined and discussed.	

A1.4.4. Lookup of individual genetic variants

#: usGdi02.1	Soft description: Lookup of individual genetic variants
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Genome of Europe use case
<p>User story description: The use case is a refinement of usGdi02 (Look up variant summary data in and across GDI datasets) to a real case scenario.</p> <p>A researcher needs to query the GDI infrastructure to know whether a specific variant linked to a certain disorder is present in a large genomic dataset collected from individuals from a particular population (e.g. region). This information could help determine if the variant is common or rare in that population, which might be important for understanding the genetic predisposition to a certain disorder.</p> <p>The goal is to find human genomic datasets for a given population and explore the frequency of a specific variant.</p> <p>Preconditions: The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). 	

#: usGdi02.1	Soft description: Lookup of individual genetic variants
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Genome of Europe use case
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher will construct a Beacon query (ujGdi03), i.e. the researcher inputs the details of the variant (genomic coordinates) into GDI's Beacon Network, asking whether the variant is present in specific population datasets and at what frequency. - The GDI returns aggregated results, which could include the list of human genomic datasets with individual participant data, together with a summary on group level (pre-computed and available through Beacon network), i.e. the frequency of the variant in the population or the percentage of people with this variant. <p>Postconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 	

A1.4.5. Cancer as a Rare Disease

<p>#: usGdi03</p>	<p>Soft description: Cancer as a Rare Disease</p>
	<p>Triggered by User Role: Clinician/oncologist</p>
	<p>Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case</p>
<p>User story description: A healthcare professional comes across an interesting case during one of their weekly Molecular Tumour Board (MTB) sessions at their institute. A pancreatic acinar cell carcinoma (PACC) patient is presented as having a complex histological pattern and an uncommon BRAF sequence alteration: V600_K601delinsE. The clinician wonders whether the patient can be treated as if he/she has a 'classical' BRAF V600E variant and searches for any other patients harbouring the non-canonical BRAF variant identified and treated at other European centres. This information would guide the decision-making process, suggesting the most suitable therapeutic choice(s) for the patient. Since the specific BRAF variant is rarely found in this kind of cancer patients, access to a broad cohort would be helpful. The clinician would like to know if any patients corresponding to this profile exist and, if so, to learn more about their clinical history, treatment and outcome.</p> <p>The goal is to search for additional data in GDI to understand whether other patients with similar clinical/molecular characteristics carrying an unusual genetic alteration in the BRAF gene have been observed and possibly treated (and how) at other European nodes. The availability of a (small) cohort of similar patients with additional information regarding the administered therapy as well as patients' responses would guide the user to choose suitable therapeutic options.</p> <p>As a clinician, I want to understand from a small cohort of similar patients how certain gene variants affect disease progression and/or response to treatment.</p> <p>Preconditions: The clinician must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clinician logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01) and browses the available datasets (ujGdi02 or ujGdi03). - The user performs a Beacon query (ujGdi03) over the aggregate level data to get the presence of the BRAF variant (V600_K601delinsE) within the GDI infrastructure (focus on pancreatic cancer). 	

<p>#: usGdi03</p>	<p>Soft description: Cancer as a Rare Disease</p>
	<p>Triggered by User Role: Clinician/oncologist</p>
	<p>Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The GDI user interface returns results, which includes datasets obtained from other patients with the same cancer type identified at multiple nodes of the network. The dataset representing this small cohort is composed of genetic and corresponding clinical data. The clinical data show how the targeted BRAF sequence alterations affect prognosis or treatment outcomes. - Assuming the presence of the variant V600_K601delinsE in only a few patients with the same cancer diagnosis, the user can extend the analysis through the Beacon both: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) at gene-level, to retrieve more patients affected by the same cancer and carrying different types of BRAF variants. b) at pan-cancer level, searching for any other cancer patients carrying the same genetic variant. - The GDI user interface returns results, which could include information regarding clinical manifestations, therapy and response to treatment - The clinician applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - The clinician downloads the dataset of the small cohort of patients (ujGdi09). 	

A1.4.6. Genetic variant risk assessment within healthcare

#: usGdi03.1	Soft description: Genetic variant risk assessment within healthcare
	Triggered by User Role: Clinician
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Infectious Diseases use case
<p>User story description:</p> <p>The use case is a refinement of usGdi03. A clinician assumes a potential monogenic cause for a patient with severe COVID-19 and needs to access additional data to understand whether it might be a monogenic condition. This would allow for a more precise estimate of the potential risk and potentially also guide treatment.</p> <p>The goal is to find individuals with a mutation in the TLR7 gene who have been diagnosed with COVID-19</p> <p>As a clinician, I want to understand from a small cohort of similar patients how mutations in a certain gene affect disease development and/or treatment resistance.</p> <p>Preconditions: The clinician must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clinician logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). - The clinician needs to prepare a query and filter for the Beacon Network (ujGdi03) for both human genomic data (i.e. SNPs, variants) and include phenotypic data associated with COVID-19 severity (i.e. hospitalisation, ICU admission, mortality), asking whether the variant is present in specific datasets . - The GDI Beacon Network returns results, which could include human genomic datasets annotated with Covid-19 severity indicators and potentially other phenotypic information, found on one or multiple nodes of the network. - The clinician applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - The clinician downloads the dataset of the small cohort with similar patients (ujGdi09). 	

A1.4.7. Metastatic Colorectal Cancer

#: usGdi04	Soft description: Metastatic Colorectal Cancer
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case
<p>User story description:</p> <p>A researcher aims to validate proposed gene signatures for the prognosis and survival of metastatic Colorectal Cancer (CRC) patients (ROS1, PIK3CA, LRP1B and FAT4) - that have not been fully confirmed in independent datasets. For this, the researcher aims to assemble retrospective cohorts from different data sources coming from different countries, including genomics and clinical data. The researcher has a pre-compiled pipeline relevant for the use case, to ensure that results are comparable.</p> <p>The goal is to validate known gene signatures and discover new ones that are associated with CRC. Specifically, the aim is to identify how these gene signatures correlate with clinical factors such as tumour location, patient age and disease stage.</p> <p>As a researcher, I want to validate the signature of specific genes as prognostic markers across multiple comparable population datasets.</p> <p>Preconditions: The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01) and browses available datasets (ujGdi02 or ujGdi03). - The researcher uses targeted search terms to filter the Central Data Catalogue (ujGdi02) such as colorectal cancer. Data are filtered to focus on the most relevant cases: CRC patients and with details concerning the patient characteristics, disease stage, diagnosis and perhaps treatment. - The GDI returns results, which could include human genomic or genetic datasets annotated with CRC diagnosis and potentially other phenotypic information, found on one or multiple nodes of the network. We note that gene panels are more frequently applied in clinical settings. 	

<p>#: usGdi04</p>	<p>Soft description: Metastatic Colorectal Cancer</p>
	<p>Triggered by User Role: Researcher</p>
	<p>Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Cancer Research use case</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - The researcher accesses genetic sequence data for further analysis. The researcher executes the analysis by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated locations (ujGdi08). The researcher can add a workflow to the secure processing environment (SPE) (ujGdi10). - The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). 	

A1.4.8. GWAS analysis

#: usGdi05	Soft description: GWAS analysis
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Infectious diseases use case
<p>User story description: A researcher needs to query the GDI infrastructure and perform a rapid Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS) in order to validate risk variants determining the severity of COVID-19. As GWAS requires large sample sizes, multiple comparable datasets are often needed.</p> <p>The goal is to find human genomic datasets that include patients with severe COVID-19. Performing a GWAS in a federated analysis scheme.</p> <p>As a researcher, I want to perform a GWAS across multiple comparable population datasets.</p> <p>Preconditions: The researcher must authenticated and authorised to GDI</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). - The researcher needs to query and filter the Central Data Catalogue (ujGdi02) for both human genomic data (i.e. SNPs, variants) and phenotypic data associated with COVID-19 severity (i.e. hospitalisation, ICU admission, mortality). - The GDI returns results, which could include human genomic datasets annotated with Covid-19 severity indicators and potentially other phenotypic information, found on one or multiple nodes of the network. - The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - The researcher accesses the annotated genetic sequence data for further analysis. The researcher executes the analysis by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated locations (ujGdi08). The researcher can add a workflow to the secure processing environment (SPE) (ujGdi10). - The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). 	

A1.4.9. GWAS analyses across federated nodes

#: usGdi05.1	Soft description: GWAS analyses across federated nodes
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - 1+MG/B1MG use case
<p>User story description: As a researcher, I want to perform a GWAS across multiple comparable population datasets. This is an extension of usGdi05.</p> <p>The goal is to identify genes associated with a particular disease or trait using provided whole genomes. The primary output of a GDI GWAS analysis is a list of P values, effect sizes and their directions generated from the association tests of all tested genetic variants with a phenotype of interest.</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI - Relevant disease or trait and WGS data must be available for cohort building (ujGdi02) <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01) - The researcher needs to define the study cohort using diseases or trait conditions (ujGdi03) - The GDI returns results, which include the list of human genomic datasets that have specified disease or traits. - The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - If a researcher gets the approval then the researcher can access genetic sequence data indirectly by using predefined GWAS pipelines. - The researcher executes the GWAS analysis by distributing GWAS pipelines to federated processing locations (ujGdi08 and ujGdi10). Individual participants' data stay within the country. - The researcher gets the relevant GWAS result data (like list of P values, Manhattan plots etc) to his research results account. 	

#: usGdi05.1	Soft description: GWAS analyses across federated nodes
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - 1+MG/B1MG use case
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). 	

A1.4.10. Recalibration of polygenic risk scores

#: usGdi06	Soft description: Recalibration of polygenic risk scores
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Genome of Europe use case
<p>User story description: As a researcher, I want to develop PRSs so that they accurately predict disease risk for individuals in a specific ancestry population.</p> <p>A researcher wants to improve the accuracy of polygenic risk scores (PRS) for predicting disease risk in a specific ancestry population. The original PRS was developed using data from another ancestry group, but the researcher needs to adjust the PRS to be effective for individuals of the specific ancestry in their study.</p> <p>The goal is to find human genomic data from multiple populations. This data includes both genetic information and health records, such as the presence or absence of the disease of interest. Subsequently, the PRS can be recalculated in the identified dataset.</p> <p>Preconditions: The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). 	

<p>#: usGdi06</p>	<p>Soft description: Recalibration of polygenic risk scores</p>
	<p>Triggered by User Role: Researcher</p>
	<p>Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Genome of Europe use case</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher will construct a Beacon query (ujGdi03), i.e. the researcher inputs the details of the variants used in the original PRS into GDI's Beacon Network, asking whether the variant is present in multiple population datasets. - The GDI returns results, which could include the list of human genomic datasets together with a summary on group level, i.e. the frequency of the variant in the population. Only datasets containing at least a predefined percentage (cutoff) of the required variants are retained. - The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - The researcher accesses genetic sequence data. The researcher executes the analysis (PRS) by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated locations (ujGdi08). The researcher can add a workflow to the secure processing environment (SPE) (ujGdi10). Individual participants' data stay within the country. - The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). 	

A1.4.11. Ancestry-specific imputation

#: usGdi07	Soft description: Ancestry-specific imputation
	Triggered by User Role: Researcher
	Authors and Contributors: From D7.5 - Genome of Europe use case
<p>User story description: A researcher wants to impute a genetic dataset using ancestry-specific reference panels</p> <p>The goal is to impute missing genetic data using a multi-ethnic reference panel (Genome of Europe-GoE), which can capture ancestry-specific genetic variants more effectively than general panels. This requires learning correlation patterns between SNPs in the GoE data (reference panel), then using these to infer (impute) the missing genotypes in a new sample. Typically $\pm 1M$ variants are measured, and then imputed towards $>40M$ variants using the correlation data.</p> <p>Preconditions: The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI</p> <p>Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). - The researcher needs to query and filter the Central Data Catalogue (ujGdi02) (filter on ancestry) for multi-ethnic reference panels. - The GDI returns results, which could include aggregated reference panels. - The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). - The researcher accesses the reference panels (aggregated data). The researcher executes the analysis (imputation of genetic datasets). - The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). 	

A1.5. Authors and Contributors

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Annex II. Generic Federated Learning Use Case - Approach and Implementation

A2.1. The Use Case Description

A2.1.1. Preconditions

Users are valid and authenticated users in the infrastructure.

A2.1.2. Postconditions

All nodes delete intermediate model updates after a fixed time (#15).

A2.1.3. Description

- **Data Catalogue.** Users log into to the main portal (#01) to access to the data catalogue (#02) to discover datasets of interest distributed across nodes (#03).
- **Data Access.** Users request permission to access and use the datasets of their interest (#04).
- **Framework Selection.** From the main portal, users access the federated analytics dashboard (#05). There they select the federated learning frameworks and the associated workflow from the available ones in the project (#06).
- **Package Model.** Users package the model to be trained including any external files required for training (#07).
- **Configuration and Submission.** At the federated analytics dashboard, the users define the federated learning experiment according to the selected framework (#08) and then submits the experiment (#12):
 - Which datasets will participate in training (#09).
 - Model to be trained (#07).
 - Model training parameters according to the selected framework (#08).
- **Setting of Federated Experiments.** After submission (#12), the experiment is orchestrated and specific jobs are sent to each involved node. This includes the aggregation (#10) and the training (#10).
- **Federated Training.** Upon reception, each involved node trains the model locally on the local dataset (#10), sending only model updates (gradients or weights) to the aggregator (#11), and receiving a new model to train according to the experiment configuration (#10). The aggregator receives partial models, aggregates them and sends them back for further training according to the experiment configuration (#11).
- **End of the Experiment.** After the aggregator aggregates the last models fitting the configuration of the experiment (#10), the aggregator and the trainers stop and the final model is stored in the user space (#13).
- **Download Results.** Users download the final aggregated model from federated analytics dashboard (#13) and use it locally for their scientific purpose (#14).

A2.2 Action granularity

#01 Access the user portal

The entrypoint of any action in GDI should be a web interface with access to any product/service GDI can provide.

#02 Access the data catalogue

The data catalogue is the place listing all the datasets included in the project. This interface will also indicate which datasets the user has requested access to.

#03 Identify datasets of interest

The data catalogue will provide a series of filtering capabilities so the user is able to identify datasets of its interest.

#04 Request access to datasets of interest

The data catalogue will provide functionally (or access to another interface providing that functionally) so the user can request access to the datasets of its interest.

#05 User access to federated analytics dashboard

All the computation management should be centralised in a single web interface. The user can enter the federated analytics dashboard from the user portal.

#06 Tool and workflow selection

The federated analytics dashboard offers a catalogue of workflows to be used, for instance, a federated learning workflow for the framework of interest to the user.

#07 Prepare files for workflow in external repository

The user can pack any necessary file to run a workflow in an external repository like GitHub or GitLab to provide a public URL when configuring the experiment.

#08 Prepare parameters for experiment

The federated analytics dashboard presents to the user all the parameters the selected workflow requires. The user can provide the parameters, including external URLs to public repositories.

#09 Match datasets with workflow

The federated analytics dashboard shows to the user the list of available datasets (the ones the user has access to) so they can select the ones to be used (analysed) in the experiment.

#10 Deployment of a part of a software in one or multiple nodes with a specific task

The federated analytics dashboard must request to run a specific software or a part of in a specific node or in a collection of nodes.

#11 Exchange of information between software in same experiment

The infrastructure should allow the running software to establish connection so, for instance, the trainers can send partial models to the aggregator and the aggregator can send aggregated models to the trainers.

#12 Workflow submission

The federated analytics dashboard analyses the parts of the workflow and creates the tasks that have to be submitted to each of the involved nodes. Then, it **test** the availability of the nodes and submits the tasks.

#13 Experiment's results retrieval

The user will collect the results of their experiment by accessing the federated analytics dashboard.

#14 Experiment's results usage

The user can use the results as pleased according to their scientific inquiries.

#15 Experiment's results cleaning process

As the experiment ends, the federated analytics dashboard triggers a cleaning process on the involved nodes to remove any intermediate file.

A2.3. Component-Component Interaction Diagram

